

Management of Cavernoma & Uterine Fibroids Patient through Family Medicine Approach – A Case Study

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Background

Cavernoma is a neurovascular malformation that can cause seizures and/or severe focal neurological deficits^{1,2}. Uterine fibroids are benign tumors of the myometrium that cause severe abdominal pain³. A 36-year-old unmarried woman with a left hypothalamus cavernoma and uterine fibroids underwent a hysterectomy. In this case, a comprehensive family medicine approach is needed to manage potential issues for the patient and also to provide support to the family – the caregivers.

Case Presentation

A 36-year-old woman has had tremors in her extremities according to her mother. Five years ago, she was diagnosed with a left hypothalamic cavernoma. Three years ago, she was diagnosed with uterine fibroids, but has already undergone a hysterectomy. Due to recurring seizures, the patient has to take anti-seizure medication regularly. This condition not only causes pain for her but also mental and physical exhaustion for her caregivers. After the hysterectomy, she has not experienced the seizure anymore. Currently, she remains bedridden and needs support to do any activity by her family.

Result and Discussion

In this case, the cavernoma location being in the left hypothalamus made it difficult to perform surgery. Other factors included clinical presentation, comorbid conditions, and the occurrence of bleeding⁴. Patient with uterine fibroids experienced severe pain, heavy bleeding, and anemia, which affected the quality of life⁵.

In addition to neurological and gynecological management, a comprehensive management was also included through family medicine approach. Her Family APGAR score was 7 initially. Family medicine approach included pneumonia vaccination, routine medication, regular check-ups, and immediate report to her family if there were symptoms causing discomfort. The family, particularly her mother, was involved in every decision related to the patient's care. Emotional support for her mother and the other family members was provided to prevent psychological fatigue. Community support was utilized, coming from church and relatives, to provide her psychological aid, so she did not feel lonely. After a year, a reassessment of the Family APGAR score was done with an increased score to 10. The patient felt more comfortable because her family was always there for her, shared various things with her, and supported her decision to undergo the hysterectomy. Her condition has now stabilized and the family's psychological fatigue has decreased (Fig. 1).

Family Genogram Ms. RSL
July, 19th 2024

Fig.1 Family Genogram of cavernoma and uterine fibroids patient.

Conclusion

In such case, a family medicine approach is needed with the hope of not only preventing the disease to get more severe but also improving the quality of life for both the patient and the family. The increase of 3 points (from 7 to 10) in the Family APGAR score indicates that family function has improved and become highly functional.

Reference

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Other important information;
Family SCREEM, Family APGAR, Family Genogram, Family Mapping, Radiology Expertise, Cavernoma Image